

Title: The Dark Figure of Crime - Crime Victimization Survey 2025
(TheDark2025)

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BACKGROUND

Malta is highly efficient in the reporting of crime with consistent reporting since 1998 and earlier through systems known as PIRS and subsequently NPS. However, formal reporting has a dark side where victims might be either afraid to report as constrained by familial, situational and safety-security parameters. The dark figure of crime can be cause for concern considering that these types of crime are the ones victims would be expected to report, especially where repeat victimisation is concerned. Thus the need for such surveys, whose aims are twofold. Primarily it is to have comparable international crime data, however another objective is to be able to compare official police data with the data that the crime victimization survey finds. This is a way of discovering the dark figure of crime.

The Department of Criminology has been consistent in the efforts to study the dark figure and why victims opt to non-reporting.

The Principal Investigators, Dr Formosa Pace and Professor Formosa have been instrumental in the authoring of the Crime Prevention Strategy, the CrimeMalta Reporting work and the Police Transformation Strategy that has resulted in the expansion of Community Policing, the setting up of Victims Support Agencies, crime awareness and other innovations.

However, 10 years have passed since the last Crime Victimization Survey and the 10-year gap is optimal to carry out this survey in 2025 to enable a long-term change analysis, correlational analysis between formal crime reporting and the non-reporting, changes affected over the past decade in policing, victim support and other initiatives.

The survey would enable policy makers and decision-makers to have a base on which to revisit crime and victimisation, draft policies, enact changes to legislation and instigate change. This survey will follow a series of attempts to carry out such victimisation studies, The previous surveys cover:

- The first run of the Crime Victimization Survey in Malta took place in 1996. This was run under the auspices of UNICRI. A total of 1000 face-to-face interviews were conducted by 10 interviewees. The survey was financed by the Ministry for Social Policy. It was run by the Institute of Forensic Studies, within the University of Malta. Unfortunately, the results of this survey were never published.
- The 1996 survey was followed in 2009 by an in-situ crime victimization survey in Dingli. This was a small-scale survey, where 300 one-to-one questionnaires were conducted, the results of which were published in 2010.
- Another survey, based on a digital setup was termed the MEPA employee Dark Figure of Crime Survey. The survey was distributed to 300 MEPA employees as a controlled case study where employees were asked to report any crimes over 5 years and whether they filed reports to Police. However, both the sample and the reply rate was too low to enable reliable analysis and the author decided that it would not be included, though the framework is now ready for a larger run post this-study.
- An EU-wide project proposal entitled “Regulation (EU) Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on European statistics on safety from crime” was not approved and such a survey planned for 2013 did not materialise.
- In 2015, a survey was carried out as part of the LEAP ESF project based on the UNICRI crime victimization survey, which together with the Dingli survey were used to draw up a new national crime victimisation survey. The study resulted in the CVS publications as part of the SeCollege project led by Dr Formosa Pace.

STUDY OVERVIEW

The Study focuses on the updating and change analysis research of the crime victimisation and unreported crimes in the Maltese Islands. It will result in the commissioning of a national survey, training of staff, and the enhancement of the national monitoring programmes in this theme.

LINK TO NATIONAL PRIORITIES

The Study directly addresses Malta's national priorities in the crime reduction domain. The requirement to monitor crime is imperative in decreasing reporting, however victims do not always report such crimes, a phenomenon known as the Dark Figure of Crime. In particular, the Study focuses on understanding victimisation, reporting and in turn implementing monitoring requirements with respect to changes affected by and to the policing and victim support services. In the long term, the gathered information that will result from this Study will contribute to cross-domain Government policies, including policies in the fields of community policing, victim support, health, arms control, incivility, civil protection and spatial planning.

OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of the Study is to update and develop the national crime victimisation study for Malta, most recently held in 2015, allowing for a 10-year cross analysis, change monitoring and crime prevention. The purpose of the Study is two-fold:

1. To carry out a national survey in 2025 that will deliver a representative mapping of the victimisation realities and the dark figure statistics and causes of non-reported crimes for the Maltese Islands;
2. To carry out change analysis between the 2015 and 2025 surveys; and
3. To provide a long-term monitoring platform for crime victimisation reporting and monitoring, comprising strategic, operational and tactical response outcomes to ensure adherence to the highest standards and best practice in crime reporting and prevention.

ACTIVITIES & RESULTS

The purpose of the Study will be achieved through a series of activities that will lead to the procurement of a new Crime Victimization Survey 2025 which . The following results will be delivered:

1. Crime Victimization Survey (this will be delivered through a service tender) Q4 2024 – Q2 2025;
2. CVS Information System (TheDarkCVS) designed by Q4 2025 (a single service tender will address the design and development requirements);
3. Results of the Study will be disseminated throughout the Study to a wide range of stakeholders and the public through an information campaign Q3 2026.

STUDY MANAGEMENT

The Study will be led by Dr Janice Formosa Pace and Professor Saviour Formosa, who will serve as the Principal Investigators. The day-to-day management of the Study will be performed by a Study Coordinator who will be employed as an RSOI on a temporary basis.

DURATION OF THE STUDY

It is envisaged that funds for the Study will be approved in Q4 of 2024. The Study will be 2 years in duration, delivering all results by Quarter 3 of 2026.

Refer to Annex: Survey 2015 that will be used as a baseline.